

Quality of Work Life in the Covid-19 Pandemic and Performance of LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province

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ABSTRACT

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the relationship between quality of work life and the performance of regular Local Government Unit (LGU) employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic. A total of 125 regular employees were selected through stratified random sampling with proportionate allocation, representing 20% of the workforce from five municipal LGUs: Matalam, Carmen, Kabacan, Mlang, and Tulunan. Findings revealed that employees were generally satisfied with the social and environmental aspects of their work settings while carrying out their tasks to fulfill organizational goals. Results further indicated that, even amid the challenges posed by the pandemic, employees experienced a good to excellent quality of work life. Correspondingly, their performance, as measured through the Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR), was rated as very satisfactory. Statistical analysis established a significant relationship between quality of work life and employee performance, suggesting that improvements in employees' work-life quality positively relate to higher performance outcomes. Overall, the study concludes that during the COVID-19 pandemic, regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato maintained favorable levels of work-life quality and demonstrated strong performance, with the two variables showing a meaningful and significant association.

Keywords: *COVID-19 pandemic, Individual Performance Commitment Review, local government units, quality of work life, performance*

INTRODUCTION

Year 2020 was described by many as one of the most difficult years in the modern history. In the article written by Schmich (2020) of the Chicago Tribute, she made it evident that people referred these times to a dreadful pandemic. The social, political, and economic disruptions caused by the pandemic were collective. Loss, grief, and anger have touched the lives of the many from all walks of life. Likewise, the COVID-19 pandemic has challenged governments around the world and exposed the failures in our social and political system. In the Philippines, the government has exhausted all its efforts to contain and combat the pandemic from implementing legislations on community quarantines to the provision of social amelioration program (SAP) to the people.

The pandemic has posed a huge challenge to Philippine labor force as many have become unable to travel to work in fear of acquiring and transmitting the virus to other people. This has required administrators, both in public and private organizations not just in the country, but in the whole world to adapt flexible working arrangements to continue safe delivery of services to the people (Rahman, Kistyano, & Surjanti, 2020). Most of workers were in work from home set up due to the COVID-19 pandemic (Vyas & Butakhieo, 2020). They added that work from home setting was quite challenging to many, especially those living in small houses as it requires a quiet and spacious workplace for them to effectively carry their job.

Meanwhile, the UNESCO (2020) described flexible work arrangements as the “alternative arrangements or schedules from the traditional work setting.” It said that flexible work arrangements should be viewed as a balanced agreement between employers and employees where the needs of each side are addressed. In its report on good workplace practices amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, the UNESCO (2020) provided some examples of flexible work arrangements for employees from flexible time such as smaller number of working hours, switching of shift, and job sharing, flexible time off such as a prolonged holiday or personal leave and reduced working hours for part-time employees to flexible roles such as telework, virtual communication, and change of responsibilities.

In the Philippines, CSC issued a Memorandum Circular No. 18, series of 2020 that all national and local government agencies have any or a combination of the following alternative work arrangements as work-from-home, skeleton (skeletal) workforce, 4-day (compressed) workweek, work shifting/flexible (staggered) working hours and other alternative work arrangements (Civil Service Commission, 2020).

Based on the initial literature review conducted by the researcher in over 33 literature on various research data bases in public administration and organization and management, it was found out that there was a plethora of studies that have looked at the quality of work-life and employees performance. Nonetheless, little efforts have been made on studies that examined the quality of work-life and employees performance amidst the flexible work arrangements in times of the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, little attention was done that determined the significant relationship between the quality of work-life and performance of government employees primarily among LGUs in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province. It is in this light that this study will be conducted to fill-in the void that confirms the significant

relationship between the two variables among the regular employees of LGU Matalam, Carmen, Kabacan, M'lang, and Tulanun in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province.

Objectives of the Study

Improving employee performance is one of the most important functions of the human resource management of any organization. If the employee performance is high, efficiency, effective and high quality of work is manifested in the organization (Goodhue, 2011).

This study generally aimed to determine the quality of work-life that the regular employees live in the selected LGUs in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province is significantly associated with their performance or not. Specifically, it attempted to:

1. describe the work arrangement of the employees during the time of COVID 19 pandemic:
 2. assess the quality of work-life of the LGU employees in terms of:
 - 2.1. work environment
 - 2.2. organization culture and climate
 - 2.3. relation and co-operation
 - 2.4. training and development
 - 2.5. facilities
 - 2.6. job satisfaction and job security
 - 2.7. autonomy of work
 - 2.8. adequacy of resources
 3. ascertain the degree of performance of the LGU employees at work in terms of:
 - 3.1. task performance
 - 3.2. contextual performance
 - 3.3. counterproductive work behavior
 4. identify the percentage accomplishment in the IPCR rating of the employee.
 5. determine the significant relationship between the quality of work-life and performance of the LGU employees.
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Significance of the Study

In the field of management, it is a basic tenet that employees are the foundation of any organization. They are undeniably significant since they are the fuel that moves the organization towards the attainment of its goals.

In public service, government employees are considered the alter egos of government officials, especially in the realization of their projects and programs. The provision of basic services to the people will not be effective and efficient if the government employees are not happy with the quality of working life in their offices. It is one of these tenets that the researcher saw the significance of the study, particularly the need to investigate the quality of work-life and productivity of the regular employees of the selected local government units in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province as well as to examine the relationship between the two variables. The researcher highly suggests that the future findings of the study will be advantageous to government officials, heads of the various offices in the chosen locale of the study, their regular employees, and future scholars who wish to explore the same research topic.

Firstly, through the study, the government officials of the selected LGUs will be informed about the quality of work-life and performance of their regular employees. The future findings will serve as a guide for government officials in making sound legislation or programs that will improve the working environment or benefits received by the employees, leading to better work performance.

Secondly, the study is important to the heads of the various offices in the selected LGUs since it will edify them on the quality of work that their employees have at work and how well they perform their jobs. This will help them to assess whether the working environment and organizational culture and climate as influenced by their management styles are effective in the observance of high employee performance or not.

Thirdly, the results of the study will enlighten the Human Resource Management Office of the selected LGUs about the issues or problems encountered by their regular employees pertinent to their quality of work-life and performance. The results will serve as a keystone for them in crafting effective enhancement training for their employees.

Lastly, the research will serve as a credible springboard for future scholars who wish to endeavor a study on the quality of work-life and employee performance. The study will give them an idea of the meaning of the constructs investigated and the framework used to theoretically and conceptually elucidate the constructs.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The research primarily endeavored to examine if there is a significant relationship between the quality of work-life and performance of the regular employees of the selected LGUs in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province or none. The study only surveyed the regular employees who were classified as permanent rank-and-file employees. Government employees of other classifications, such as the heads or

the contractual or job order employees were no longer included in the conduct of the study. Moreover, the conduct of the study only concentrated on selected municipalities in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province, namely Matalam, Carmen, Kabacan, M'lang, and Tulan. The municipality of Banisilan was not included in the research coverage because of its accessibility.

Furthermore, the LGU offices that were included in the study were the Office of the Municipal Mayor, Sangguniang Bayan, Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator, Municipal Civil Registrar, Municipal Budget Officer, Municipal Accountant, Municipal Treasurer, Municipal Assessor, Office of the Municipal Social Welfare and Development, Municipal Health Officer, Municipal Agriculturist, Municipal Engineer, Market and Slaughterhouse, Municipal General Services Officer, and Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction Management.

Operational Definition of Terms

The following terms were defined according to their usage in the study to establish a better understanding of the constructs that were investigated in the research:

Adequacy of Resources is the extent of availability of materials, supplies, and communication and information channels for the employees necessary in facilitating performance and attainment of the organizational objectives.

Autonomy of Work is the independence that the employees observe at work in the performance of their task with less or without managerial or colleague assistance.

Compensation and Rewards is the motivational factors established by the management to improve the performance of the employees such as giving remuneration, rewards, promotions, and recognition.

Contextual Performance is the pro-social behavior demonstrated by employees in a work setup.

Counterproductive Work Behavior is employee's behavior of disobeying work rules and norms making it difficult for the organization to attain its objectives.

Employee Performance is an employee's work achievement after putting in the necessary effort at work, which is related to obtaining meaningful work, engaging profile, and surrounding compassionate colleagues/employers around.

Facilities is the desirable amenities or useful services provided by the management of the organization to their employees in the accomplishment of their tasks.

Job Satisfaction and Job Security is the employees view of how favorable or unfavorable their work to them such as the job design, their working conditions, and managerial and colleague support.

Organizational Culture and Climate is the ways of interaction and collective behavior observed by the employees at work.

Performance is the effective efforts and outcomes and negative behaviors that an employee render at work in attaining or undermining the organizational objectives.

Quality of Work Life is the degree to which the employee is happy and contented with social and professional environment of his or her organization while performing tasks in the achievement of the objectives of the entire organization.

Rank and File Employees is the employees in organization who are not in any leadership or managerial positions.

Relation and Cooperation is the communication between the employees and their heads necessary in making decisions and resolving conflicts and problems that arise in the organization.

Task Performance is the employee's job explicit behaviors which include fundamental job responsibilities assigned as a part of job description.

Training and Development is the activities held by the management of the various offices in pursuit of improving the performance of their employees.

Working Environment is the social and professional setting where the employees work, interact, and coordinate with their colleagues.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Quality of Work Life

In every industry, the quality of work-life is becoming increasingly important in meeting organizational goals (Yadav & Khanna, 2014). It can be explained as the degree of employee needs, both personal and professional are met by participating in various work activities while attaining the organization's objectives. Feldman (2011) said that quality of work-life can be understood by looking into strength of relationship that employees have with their whole working environment. Quality of work-life is reflected in a working environment where rewards, job stability, and possibilities for career advancement were provided among employees to increase job satisfaction (Lau, Wong, Chan, & Law, 2011).

Moreover, Leitão et al. (2019) explained that although job satisfaction and career achievement are important indicators, quality of work-life is found to be associated with job enrichment and work motivation. It was also noted that it can be increased by improving employee pay and encouraging growth opportunities and promotion.

Furthermore, Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015) indicated that several interventions can be utilized in improving the quality of life of the employees such as implementing flexible time arrangements, job enrichment and enlargement and developing an independent group work setting. Louis and Smith (2011)

point out that quality of work-life can also predicts employee turnover and well-being which otherwise influence the quality of services offered by the organization. Quality of work-life can also be used in redesigning a job by improving the social and technical dimensions of work. Enhancing the quality of life of the employees benefits both employees and organization.

Dimensions of Quality of Work Life

Examining quality of work-life has increased the attention of researchers as numerous studies found that it is significantly associated with important organizational concepts such as job satisfaction, job security, and work motivation. In investigating the construct, Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015) indicated that it is multifaceted. Reddy and Reddy (2014) added that it can be measured by assessing the employee's work conditions, remuneration, sense of worth at work, and opportunities for professional growth. Sharma and Verma (2013) added employee's communication, flexibility of working time, work motivation, and job satisfaction as indicators of quality of work-life. In ascertaining the construct, the researcher described the quality of work-life according to the conceptualization of Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015). Each dimension is discussed in the succeeding paragraphs.

Work Environment

Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015) referred working environment basically to the place where employees do their jobs. It includes the social and professional atmosphere of work where employees interact with their supervisor, colleagues, and clients. A good working condition resonates an environment where employees have good health, enjoy a stable job, and healthy management relations. If employees work in a healthy environment, high productivity is ensured. Making the employees' working hours reasonable makes them feel that their physical and mental working environment is safe. Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015) indicated that it makes employees happy and confident about their job making them the strength of their organization.

Organization Culture and Climate

Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015) defined organizational culture as the set of characteristics and type of structure an organization has while organization climate encompasses the behavior of the members of the organization that form up the organization's vision, values, and standards. The organizational climate can also be understood through its policies. An example of it is on how managers make polices on promotion opportunities to control the performance of the employees.

Relation and Co-Operation

The type of communication that employees have with the management defines relation and cooperation. It includes mechanisms in improving workplace decision, addressing problems, and resolving conflicts. Socialization is important for employees to be able to achieve their work, particularly in communicating with other members of the organization. The degree of personal and professional relationships that employees have at work is an important criterion of quality of work-life. Employee

acceptance at the workplace based on their skills and traits related to work regardless of their socio-demographic profile is important indicator of the quality of work-life (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Swamy, 2015).

Training and Development

Training and Development is an essential element of professional growth. It is an activity of the organization that improves the knowledge and skills of the employees resulting to higher employee performance. Along with healthy working condition, equal opportunity for training among employees ensures quality of work life. The encouragement for training and development should first come from the management. This would make the employees feel more empowered at work (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Swamy, 2015).

Facilities

Facilities serve as the instrument in realizing the goals and objectives of an organization. Employees can fulfill their physical and emotional needs through their work facilities such as security, transportation, and food service. Various employers see the relevance of flexible work arrangements in enhancing work ethics and job productivity. Such includes work at home setting, shorter or flexible working time, and safe working environment (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Swamy, 2015).

Job Satisfaction and Job Security

Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015) indicated that how favorable the work with the employees resembles job satisfaction. The design of the employees' job influences their job satisfaction. Elements that induce positive behavior such as effective communication, autonomy at work organizational sense of belongingness, and task variety predict job satisfaction. Moreover, job security is also an important determinant in job satisfaction. Employees desire that their employment is stable. Policies that encourage job security reflect the quality of work-life.

Autonomy of Work

Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015) defined autonomy of work as the extent that employees have the freedom to decide about their work. It means that employees are allowed to participate in planning and engage at various activities at work. Autonomy of work also allows employees to speak out their thought to improve working conditions. They are given a chance to talk to their colleagues and supervisors as to how to address some issues at work. It also comprises personnel empowerment and opportunity to access some work-related information or obtain an experience necessary for completing their tasks.

Adequacy of Resources

The objectives of the organization should be congruent with the number of resources it has both material and human resources. If the resources are inadequate, the employees will not be able to achieve the objectives set before the organization, and it will adversely affect the entire organization. Some of the

unpleasant consequences are poor employee job satisfaction and quality of work-life. Adequacy of resources also comprises the amount of information and time that employees must achieve their work within a specific period (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Swamy, 2015).

The Concept of Performance

Employee performance is one of the most examined constructs in the epistemology of organizational sciences. Campbell (2011) indicated that it consists of both positive and negative behaviors of employees in achieving or undermining the organizational objectives. Hellriegel et al. (2010) termed it as the employee's effort in achieving a particular work through compassion of his or her workmates, managerial support, and job engagement as well as the meaningfulness of work. Viswesvaran et al. (2011) added that it is linked with the effective efforts and work outcomes contribution of each employee at work in attaining the goals of the organization. Organ (2011) added that it is important to broaden the construct and add extra-role dimensions to further understand it such as the role of cooperation between employees and their superiors in fulfilling a particular job. Organ (2011) also discussed that it is important to look into the organizational citizenship behaviors of employees. Moreover, Sarmiento and Beale (2011) defined employee performance as the combination of the abilities and skills of employees and their motivation to use them to complete their tasks.

Dimensions of Employee Performance

Furthermore, Koopmans et al. (2014) conceptualized employee performance as a multifaceted construct. Several indicators of the construct were proposed by scholars such as employee's behavior towards the clientele, empowerment, and collaboration (Pradhan & Jena, 2016), proactivity, participation in problem solving, and implementation of work-related ideas (Parker, Williams, & Turner, 2011). Koopmans et al. (2014) indicated that the dimensions of employee performance include task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior. This study will employ the dimensions provided by said scholars in examining employee performance.

Task Performance

Task performance is defined as the employee's job behaviors in completing their work responsibilities as indicated in the description of their job. It basically requires the cognitive ability of an employee and is guided by his or her technical knowledge of the task. It also includes one's ability to handle many work assignments effectively with lesser or no supervision. Conway (2011) said that it includes the employee's intrinsic ability to respond to the given task assigned to him or her resulting to performance. It is one's ability to perform a specific task prior to experiencing it.

In an organization, task performance refers to the understanding that an employee has with the task assigned to him or her by the manager. It can be a technical administrative or leadership task performance (Tripathy, 2014). Technical administrative task performance includes planning, organizing, and managing work while leadership task performance includes keeping organizational work standards as well as

establishing strategies that motivate and direct employees in achieving their job such as proper mentoring and giving employee recognition.

Contextual Performance

Contextual performance is an altruistic behavior that employees exhibit at work. Contrary to task performance, contextual performance includes employee's job behaviors that are not specified in their job description. Brief and Motowidlo (2011) defined it as an employee's behavior that is directed to encourage an employee, group, or organization for betterment. Contextual performance is subdivided into two dimensions – the work that is required by the organization to an employee in fulfilling one's role and the voluntary behavior exhibited by an employee at work that benefits the organization such as commitment, teamwork, and determination (Borman & Motowidlo, 2011). The term was coined by psychologists to refer to one's discretionary behavior to help others perform their job responsibilities. Employees who exhibit contextual performance volunteer for extra job, work with enthusiasm and help and cooperate with others; hence, they contribute to the overall health of the organization.

Counterproductive Work Behavior

Scholars vary in defining counterproductive work behavior (Glińska-Noweś & Lis, 2016), but what is common in literature is it substantively constitute the opposite of extra productive behaviors at work such as the organizational citizenship behavior (Organ, 2011). The vacuum of concrete definition of the construct makes it difficult to understand. Szostek (2017) associated it with terms such as adverse, unethical or retaliating work behaviors. There is still no definite behavior that forms it, but Nerdinger (2011) said that what researchers agreed is that it is characterized by one's disobedience of work rules and norms making it difficult for the organization to attain its objectives. Koopmans et al. (2014) cited that it is a collection of adverse discretionary behavior at work that are or may jeopardize the organization and its clientele. It may start with minor misconduct such as gossiping or theft and end with serious offences such as verbal or physical harassment or swindling.

Relationship between Quality of Work Life and Employee Performance

Very limited studies were conducted that significantly associated quality of work-life and employee performance. Some of them were done by Hamad (2018) and Cross and Daniel (2020). In the study of Hamad (2018), a positive and meaningful relationship was determined between employee performance and quality of work life. Moreover, Cross and Daniel (2020) found that quality of work-life is positively and significantly related to employee job performance which in turn affects organizational performance. Cross and Daniel (2020) suggested that if an organization has good quality of work-life, its procedures and policies can be effectively managed.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the proposition of Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015) that quality of work-life is investigated as a multidimensional construct in reference with the conceptualization of

Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015). Accordingly, quality of work-life is viewed in nine dimensions comprising the employees' work environment, organization culture and climate, relation and co-operation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction and job security, autonomy of work, and adequacy of resources.

Moreover, there are various theories or paradigms that elucidate employee performance. Firstly, the ideas laid in the study about employee performance corroborate with the theory of work performance of Blumberg and Pringle (2012). According to their theory, the ability to perform refers to physiological and cognitive abilities that enable an individual to perform effectively. Examples are personal knowledge, skills, intelligence, health, and stamina. Psychological traits and emotions that affect the degree of an individual's ability to perform each task refer to their willingness to perform the tasks. Motivation can be associated with the impact of expectations on work satisfaction, personality, work involvement, attitudes, and perceptual roles (Blumberg & Pringle, 2012).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. *The conceptual framework of the study shows the hypothesized relationship between the quality of work-life and performance of the respondents.*

This diagram was the conceptual framework of the study. The study primarily tried to answer the question of whether a meaningful relationship is observed between the quality of work-life and performance of the respondents or not. To elucidate the hypothesized correlation between the two variables, a paradigm was illustrated where two circles are shown and connected by a single arrow.

The study specifically attempted to determine the quality of work-life of the regular employees of LGU Matalam, Carmen, Kabacan, M'lang, and Tulanun. Quality of work-life was investigated as a multidimensional construct in reference to the conceptualization of Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015). Accordingly, quality of work-life was viewed in nine dimensions comprising the employees' work environment, organization culture and climate, relation and co-operation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction and job security, autonomy of work, and adequacy of resources.

Furthermore, the research aimed to determine the degree of performance of the regular employees of the selected LGUs in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province. Similarly, the researcher attempted to examine the construct using several dimensions in pursuit of not containing it as a single idea. Accordingly, employee performance cannot be viewed using a single lens; instead, it is understood as a multifaceted construct which comprises task performance, conceptual performance, and counterproductive work behavior.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses of the study were tested at a .05 level of significance:

1. The quality of work-life of the regular employees is not significantly related to their employees' performance.
2. The quality of work-life of the regular employees is not significantly related to the Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) Rating.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used descriptive research design and correlational technique. A descriptive research design was utilized in the study to determine the quality of work-life of the regular employees in LGU Matalam, Carmen, Kabacan, M'lang, and Tulanun in terms of their work environment, organization culture and climate, relation and co-operation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction and job security, autonomy of work, and adequacy of resources. It will also be employed to determine the degree of performance of the regular employees at work in terms of; task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior. On the other hand, a correlational technique was used to determine if there is a significant relationship between the quality of work-life and performance of the regular employees in LGU Matalam, Carmen, Kabacan, M'lang, and Tulanun.

Locale of the Study

This research was done in the selected local government units in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province, such as the municipalities of Matalam, Carmen, Kabacan, M'lang, and Tulunan.

Specifically, the study was conducted in various LGU offices such as the Office of Municipal Mayor, Sangguniang Bayan, Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator, Municipal Civil Registrar, Municipal Budget Officer, Municipal Accountant, Municipal Treasurer, Municipal Assessor, Municipal Social Welfare and Development, Municipal Health Officer, Municipal Agriculturist, Municipal Engineer, Market and Slaughterhouse, and Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction Management.

The municipality of Matalam is divided into 34 barangays. Moreover, according to the 2015 data provided by the Philippine Statistics, Matalam is lived by 79,361 people whose native language is mostly Cebuano and Hiligaynon. Furthermore, according to the report provided by the Bureau of Local Government Finance, it is a firstclass municipality with a yearly revenue of Php196,475,685.66 for the fiscal year 2016.

Moreover, Tulunan is divided into 29 barangays. According to the 2015 data provided by the Philippines Statistics, inhabited by 56,513 people and has a land area of 343.08 sq. km. In terms of economy, the yearly revenue of Tulunan for the fiscal year of 2016 was ₱150,386,965.68 according to the Bureau of Local Government Finance.

Furthermore, M'lang is divided into 37 barangays. According to the 2015 data provided by the Philippine Statistics, M'lang is lived by 95,070 people and has a land area of 312.13 sq. km.. According to the Bureau of Local Government Finance, the yearly revenue of M'lang for the fiscal year of 2016 was ₱209,327,651.28.

Moreover, Kabacan is a first class municipality that is mainly composed of rice farms and inhabited by an influx of Ilocano-speaking people from Northern Philippines. The yearly revenue of Kabacan for the fiscal year of 2016 was ₱231,542,099.78 according to the report of the Bureau of Local Government Finance. Kabacan has a population of 89,161 people according to the 2015 census of the Philippine Statistics Authority.

Lastly, Carmen is a first class municipality located in the landlocked province of Cotabato whose industries are mostly agricultural based. The yearly revenue of Carmen was ₱292,313,215.08 for the fiscal year of 2016 according to the report of the Bureau of Local Government Finance. Carmen has a population of 95,921 people according to the 2015 census of the Philippine Statistics Authority.

Figure 2. *The Map of the 3rd District of Cotabato Province*

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the regular or permanent employees, rank-and-file, and worked in the office where they were designated for a year in various offices in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province. Specifically, they work in the Office of the Municipal Mayor, Sangguniang Bayan, Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator, Municipal Civil Registrar, Municipal Budget Officer, Municipal Accountant, Municipal Treasurer, Municipal Assessor, Municipal Social Welfare and Development, Municipal Health Officer, Municipal Agriculturist, Municipal Engineer, Market and Slaughterhouse, Municipal General Services Officer, and Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction Management.

Furthermore, the breakdown of regular employees in every LGU is as follows:

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents by Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province, March 2021

<i>Municipality</i>	<i>Number of Employees (Population)</i>	<i>Number of Sample (20% of the Population)</i>
Matalam	95	19
Tulunan	101	20
M'lang	119	23
Kabacan	142	28
Carmen	175	35
Total	632	125

There was a total of 125 respondents who participated in the study.

Sampling Method

The respondents of this research were the regular employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province. In determining the sample for the study, the researcher used stratified random sampling with proportionate allocation by taking 20% of the LGU employees in each municipality chosen in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province, namely Tulunan, Matalam, M'lang, Kabacan, and Carmen.

Research Instruments

The researcher used a survey questionnaire to gather data from the regular employees in the selected LGUs in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province. The survey questionnaire was divided into three components. Firstly, some general information about the respondents will be asked of them. It comprises their name, age, sex, and years of service. Answering the employee's profile will be optional for the respondents, especially their names.

Secondly, the survey questionnaire determined the degree of quality of work- life of the respondents in terms of their work environment, organization culture and climate, relation and co-operation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction and job security, autonomy of work, and adequacy of resources. This section of the instrument was modified from the research of Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2015).

Lastly, the third component of the instrument determined the degree of performance of the respondents in terms of their task performance, conceptual performance, and counterproductive work behavior. This part of the questionnaire was modified from the study of Koopmans et al. (2014).

Data Gathered and Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathered in the study was the quality of work-life and performance of the respondents at work. These data were all primary data since they were all taken directly from the respondents by asking them to fill-out a survey questionnaire that resonates the quality of work-life and employee performance that they have at work.

Moreover, the quality of work-life and employee performance were treated as ordinal data since the researcher used a four-point Likert type scale in measuring the two variables, with one as the most negative response and four as the most positive response. Furthermore, the two variables were measured using an ordinal scale since equidistance among the values is not established in the scale.

Meanwhile, all the items in the survey questionnaire that attempted to determine the quality of work-life of the regular employees were measured using a four-point Likert type scale that ranges from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree). The researcher utilized the Likert-type scale provided by Brown (2012) of Iowa State University Extension.

Response Scale	Qualitative Description
4	Strongly Agree
3	Agree
2	Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

Furthermore, all the items in the survey questionnaire that determined the degree of performance of the regular employees were measured through a four-point Likert type scale that ranges from 1 (Never) to 4 (Always). The Likert-type scale that was used was adopted from the study of Brown (2012) of Iowa State University Extension.

Response Scale	Qualitative Description
4	Always
3	Often
2	Rarely
1	Never

On the other hand, the researcher followed a step-by-step process in collecting study data. First, the researcher made a request letter submitted to the concerned authorities allowing to conduct the study. The researcher sent a letter to the Dean of Graduate School allowing him to conduct the study after it is successfully defended and prepared for conduct. Afterwards, the student sent a letter to the Office of the Municipal Mayor of the selected LGUs allowing to conduct the study, COVID-19 protocols like wearing of facemask, face shield and social distancing were observed. All the letters contained a confidentiality and anonymity clause that concealed the identities and responses of the respondents to the statements in the questionnaire.

Once the letter is approved, the researcher proceeded to the concerned offices. Nevertheless, he followed all of the health protocols implemented by the office such as wearing of face mask and shield, sanitizing hands, and observing social distancing.

The researcher personally distributed the questionnaires to the respondents and gave enough time to read and personally reflect on the items. After filling-out, the researcher collected the questionnaires and thanked the respondents for their time in participating in the study.

Method of Data Analysis

The data from the study was analyzed using various statistical tools.

Frequency and percentage were used to identify the work arrangements of the respondents during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The *mean* was used to determine the quality of work-life of the respondents in terms of their work environment, organization culture and climate, relation and co-operation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction and job security, autonomy of work, and adequacy of resources. It will also be utilized to determine their degree of employee performance in terms of task performance, conceptual performance, and counterproductive work behavior.

Furthermore, the *Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient* was used to determine if there was a significant relationship between the quality of work life and performance of the respondents. As explained in the data gathered section, the data of the study was treated as ordinal data since equidistance in each value on the scale used is not observed. Moreover, the data gathered for the quality of work-life of the respondents were analyzed using a scale which was modified from the study of Brown (2012) of Iowa State University Extension. The value allocations and their corresponding interpretations are presented below.

Mean Scale	Interpretation
3.26-4.00	Excellent
2.51-3.25	Good
1.76-2.50	Fair
1.00-1.75	Poor

Lastly, the data gathered for the employee performance of the respondents were analyzed through a scale which was modified from the study of Brown (2012) of Iowa State University Extension. The value allocations and their corresponding interpretations were presented below.

Mean Scale	Interpretation
3.26-4.00	High
2.51-3.25	Moderate
1.76-2.50	Low
1.00-1.75	None

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Work Arrangements of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic

The pandemic of COVID-19 has challenged organizations both in the private and public sector in providing services to their clientele as many have become unable to travel to work in fear of acquiring and transmitting the virus to other people. The Philippine government has mandated local government agencies and institutions to shift from traditional face-to-face work to flexible working arrangements to continue quality yet safe service delivery (Rahman, Kistyano, & Surjanti, 2020).

Table 2 presents the work arrangements of the regular LGU employees during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study identified that most of the respondents comprising 84.80% of the sample, observed a five-day working arrangement, namely; Kabacan, M'lang, Tulanun, and Carmen, while LGU Matalam

observed a four-day working arrangement, representing 15.20% of the sample. None of the respondents were identified to work under a skeletal working arrangement.

Table 2
Work Arrangements of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Working Arrangement	Frequency (n=125)	Percentage
4-day Work	19	15.20%
5-day Work	106	84.80%

Quality of Work Life of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic

In all industries, quality of work-life is a significant indicator of organizational performance (Yadav & Khanna, 2014). Several studies found it to be associated with job enrichment and work motivation (Leitão, Pereira, & Gonçalves, 2019). Feldman (2011) explained it as the degree of employee needs, both personal and professional, are achieved as they participate in organizational activities.

This section presents the quality of work-life of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during COVID-19 pandemic in terms of work environment, organization culture and climate, relation and cooperation, training and development, facilities, job satisfaction and job security, autonomy of work, and adequacy of resources. Afterwards, the overall finding on the quality of work life of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic followed.

Quality of Work Life in terms of Work Environment of the Regular Employees

Table 3.a presents the quality of work-life in terms of work environment of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Based on their responses, M’lang LGU employees had an excellent quality of work environment (mean=3.43). This implies that they had an exceptional social and professional setting where they could work, interact, and coordinate with their colleagues. Moreover, the finding is primarily attributed to the enough information provided to them by the LGU to discharge their responsibilities (mean=3.52), numerous work empowerment given to them to choose their own style and working pace (mean=3.48), and good and highly motivating LGU work environment (mean=3.48).

Likewise, Carmen LGU employees had an excellent quality of work environment (mean=3.30). This implies that they had an exceptional social and professional setting where they could work, interact, and coordinate with their colleagues. Furthermore, the finding is primarily attributed to the good and highly motivating LGU work environment (mean=3.49) and working conditions (mean=3.43).

Tulunan LGU employees also had a good quality of work environment (mean=3.18). This implies that they had a desirable social and professional setting where they could work, interact, and coordinate with their colleagues. Furthermore, the finding is primarily attributed to the numerous work empowerment given to them to choose their own style and working pace (mean=3.40), good and highly motivating LGU work environment (mean=3.30), and enough information provided to them by the LGU to discharge their responsibilities (mean=3.30).

Matalam LGU employees had a good quality of work environment (mean=3.15). This implies that they had a desirable social and professional setting where they could work, interact, and coordinate with their colleagues. Moreover, the finding is primarily attributed to their good and highly motivating LGU work environment (mean=3.47) and working conditions (mean=3.37).

Kabacan LGU employees had a good quality of work environment (mean=3.10). This implies that they had a desirable social and professional setting where they could work, interact, and coordinate with their colleagues. Moreover, the finding is primarily attributed to their good and highly motivating LGU work environment (mean=3.46) and working conditions (mean=3.36).

Table 3.a

The Quality of Work Life in terms of Work Environment of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD
During the COVID-19 pandemic,												
1. My LGU work environment is good and highly motivating.	3.47	SA	3.49	SA	3.46	SA	3.48	SA	3.30	SA	3.44	SA
2. Working conditions are good in my LGU.	3.37	SA	3.43	SA	3.36	SA	3.43	SA	3.20	A	3.36	SA
3. It is hard to take time off during our work to take care of personal or family matters.	2.63	A	2.83	A	2.71	A	3.26	SA	2.80	A	2.85	A
4. My LGU offers sufficient opportunities to develop my own abilities	3.11	A	3.37	SA	2.96	A	3.39	SA	3.10	A	2.85	A

5. The LGU provides enough information to discharge my responsibilities	3.11	A	3.31	SA	3.00	A	3.52	SA	3.30	SA	3.25	A
6. I am given a lot of work empowerment to decide about my own style and pace of work.	3.21	A	3.34	SA	3.07	A	3.48	SA	3.40	SA	3.30	SA
Overall	3.15	A	3.30	SA	3.10	A	3.43	SA	3.18	A	3.23	A

LEGEND:	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Agree (A)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Poor (P)

Quality of Work Life in terms of Organization Culture and Climate of the Regular Employees

Table 3.b presents the quality of work-life in terms of organization culture and climate of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

LGU employees of Carmen had a good quality of organization culture and climate (mean=3.23). This implies that they observed desirable ways of interaction and collective behavior at work. Moreover, the finding is attributed to the cooperation observed between all departments to achieve goals (mean=3.63) and their pride in working for their present LGU (mean=3.57).

Tulunan LGU employees also had a good quality of organization culture and climate (mean=3.14). This implies that they observed desirable ways of interaction and collective behavior at work. Moreover, the finding is attributed to their pride in working for their present LGU (mean=3.80) and communication of the LGU of every new change that takes place (mean=3.60).

M'lang LGU employees had good quality of organization culture and climate (mean=3.12). This implies that they observed desirable ways of interaction and collective behavior at work. Moreover, the finding is attributed to the cooperation observed between all departments to achieve goals (mean=3.57) and their pride in working for their present LGU (mean=3.52).

Matalam LGU employees had good quality of organization culture and climate (mean=3.07). This implies that they observed desirable ways of interaction and collective behavior at work. Further, the finding is attributed to their pride in working for their present LGU (mean=3.58), communication of the LGU of every new change that takes place (mean=3.37), and good wage policies adopted by the LGU (mean=3.37).

Kabacan LGU employees had a good quality of organization culture and climate (mean=2.93). This implies that they observed desirable ways of interaction and collective behavior at work. Moreover, the finding is attributed to their pride in working for their present LGU (mean=3.57) and cooperation observed between all departments to achieve goals (mean=3.32).

Table 3.b

The Quality of Work Life in terms of Organization Culture and Climate of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD										
During the COVID-19 pandemic,												
1. There is cooperation among all the departments for achieving the goals.	3.32	SA	3.63	SA	3.32	SA	3.57	SA	3.50	SA	3.47	SA
2. I feel free to offer comments and suggestions on my performance.	3.26	SA	3.31	SA	2.89	A	3.43	SA	3.20	A	3.22	A
3. I am proud to be working for my present LGU.	3.58	SA	3.57	SA	3.57	SA	3.52	SA	3.80	SA	3.61	SA
4. I am involved in making decisions that affect our work.	3.21	A	3.37	SA	2.89	A	3.35	SA	3.40	SA	3.24	A
5. I am discriminated on my job because of my gender.	1.37	SA	2.11	D	1.61	SD	1.26	SD	1.10	SD	1.49	SD
6. The wage policies adopted by my LGU are good.	3.37	SA	3.37	SA	3.14	A	3.30	SA	3.40	SA	3.32	SA
7. The LGU communicates every new change that takes place.	3.37	SA	3.51	SA	3.11	A	3.43	SA	3.60	SA	3.42	SA
Overall	3.07	A	3.23	A	2.93	A	3.12	A	3.14	A	3.10	A

LEGEND:	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Agree (A)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Poor (P)

Quality of Work Life in terms of Relation and Cooperation of the Regular Employees

Table 3.c presents the quality of work-life in terms of relation and cooperation of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Based on their responses, Tulunan LGU employees had an excellent quality of relation and cooperation at work (mean=3.53). This implies that there was exceptional communication between the employees and heads necessary in making decisions and resolving conflicts and problems that arise in their organization. Further, the finding is attributed to their harmonious relationship with their colleagues (mean=3.90), very good relationship between head of office and employees (mean=3.80), and their very cordial relationship with their immediate supervisor (mean=3.80).

Likewise, M'lang LGU employees had an excellent quality of relation and cooperation at work (mean=3.38). This implies that there was exceptional communication between the employees and heads necessary in making decisions and resolving conflicts and problems that arise in their organization. Further, the finding is attributed to their harmonious relationship with their colleagues (mean=3.65), strong sense of belongingness in their LGU (mean=3.43), and very good relationship between head of office and employees (mean=3.43).

Kabacan LGU employees also had a good quality of relation and cooperation at work (mean=3.25). This implies that there was a desirable communication between the employees and heads necessary in making decisions and resolving conflicts and problems that arise in their organization. Moreover, the finding is attributed to the good support they get from their subordinates (mean=3.57) and their harmonious relationship with their colleagues (mean=3.46).

Likewise, Carmen LGU employees had a good quality of relation and cooperation at work (mean=3.24). This implies that there was a desirable communication between the employees and heads necessary in making decisions and resolving conflicts and problems that arise in their organization. Moreover, the finding is attributed to the very good relationship between head of office and employees (mean=3.60) and good support they get from their subordinates (mean=3.49).

Matalam LGU employees had a good quality of relation and cooperation at work (mean=3.12). This implies that there was a desirable communication between the employees and heads necessary in making decisions and resolving conflicts and problems that arise in their organization. Moreover, the finding is attributed to the very good relationship between head of office and employees (mean=3.42) and good support they get from their subordinates (mean=3.32).

Table 3.c

The Quality of Work Life in terms of Relation and Cooperation of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD
During the COVID-19 pandemic,												
1. There is a harmonious relationship with my colleagues.	3.26	SA	3.20	A	3.46	SA	3.65	SA	3.90	SA	3.49	SA
2. There is a strong sense of belongingness in my LGU.	3.26	SA	3.23	A	3.25	A	3.43	SA	3.60	SA	3.35	SA
3. I am unable to attend to my personal work due to the demands made by my job.	2.26	D	2.57	A	2.61	A	3.00	A	2.50	D	2.59	A
4. The relationship between head of office and employees are very good.	3.42	SA	3.60	SA	3.39	SA	3.43	SA	3.80	SA	3.53	SA
5. There is a very cordial relationship with my immediate supervisor.	3.21	A	3.37	SA	3.21	A	3.35	SA	3.80	SA	3.39	SA
6. I get good support from my subordinates.	3.32	SA	3.49	SA	3.57	SA	3.39	SA	3.60	SA	3.47	SA
Overall	3.12	A	3.24	A	3.25	A	3.38	SA	3.53	SA	3.30	SA

LEGEND:

Response Scale

4
3
2
1

Mean (M)

3.26-4.00
2.51-3.25
1.76-2.50
1.00-1.75

Qualitative Description (QD)

Strongly Agree (SA)
Agree (A)
Disagree (D)
Strongly Disagree (SD)

Interpretation

Excellent (E)
Good (G)
Fair (F)
Poor (P)

Quality of Work Life in terms of Training and Development of the Regular Employees

Table 3.d presents the quality of work-life in terms of training and development of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Based on their responses, Tulanang LGU employees enjoyed an excellent quality of training and development (mean=3.43). This implies that the activities held by the management of the various offices in pursuit of improving the performance of their employees were outstanding. Moreover, the finding is ascribed to the frequent conduct of training programs (mean=3.50), helpfulness of the training programs to the employees acquire the skillsthey need to perform their job effectively (mean=3.40), aim of the training programs at improving interpersonal relationship among employees (mean=3.40), and sufficient training opportunities offered by the LGU to perform the job competently (mean=3.40).

Likewise, Carmen LGU employees enjoyed an excellent quality of training and development (mean=3.31). This implies that the activities held by the management of the various offices in pursuit of improving the performance of their employees were outstanding. Moreover, the result is attributed to the frequent conduct of training programs (mean=3.34), helpfulness of the training programs to the employees acquire the skillsthey need to perform their job effectively (mean=3.31), and sufficient training opportunities offered by the LGU to perform the job competently (mean=3.31).

Kabacan LGU employees enjoyed an excellent quality of training and development (mean=3.28). This implies that the activities held by the management of the various offices in pursuit of improving the performance of their employees were outstanding. Moreover, the finding is ascribed to thehelpfulness of the training programs in helping the employees acquire the skills they need to perform their job effectively(mean=3.39) and frequent conduct of training programs (mean=3.32).

Matalam LGU employees also enjoyed a good quality of training and development (mean=3.43). This implies that the activities held by the management of the various offices in pursuit of improving the performance of their employees were desirable. Moreover, the finding is attributed to the frequent conduct of training programs (mean=3.11) and helpfulness of the training programs to the employees in acquiring the skillsthey need to perform their job effectively(mean=2.95).

Table 3.d

The Quality of Work Life in terms of Training and Development of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD
During the COVID-19 pandemic,												
1. Training programs in our LGU help employees to achieve the required skill for performing the job effectively.	2.95	A	3.31	SA	3.39	SA	2.96	A	3.40	SA	3.40	A
2. The training programs aim at improving interpersonal relationship among employees.	2.89	A	3.26	SA	3.25	A	3.00	A	3.40	SA	3.16	A
3. My LGU offers sufficient training opportunities to perform my job competently.	2.79	A	3.31	SA	3.14	SA	2.87	A	3.40	SA	3.10	A
4. The training programs are conducted frequently.	3.11	A	3.34	SA	3.32	SA	SA	A	3.50	SA	3.28	SA
Overall	2.94	A	3.31	SA	3.28	SA	2.99	A	3.43	SA	3.19	A

LEGEND:	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Agree (A)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Poor (P)

Quality of Work Life in terms of Facilities of the Regular Employees

Table 3.e presents the quality of work-life in terms of facilities of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Based on their responses, Carmen LGU employees enjoyed an excellent quality of facilities at work (mean=3.40). This implies that there were exceptional amenities or useful services provided by the management of the organization to their employees in the accomplishment of their tasks. Furthermore, the finding is mainly attributed to the good welfare activities (mean=3.54) and good safety measures adopted by the LGU (mean=3.51).

Likewise, M'lang LGU employees enjoyed an excellent quality of facilities at work (mean=3.38). This implies that there were exceptional amenities or useful services provided by the management of the organization to their employees in the accomplishment of their tasks. The finding is primarily ascribed to the good safety measures (mean=3.57) and good welfare activities provided by the LGU (mean=3.43).

Moreover, Tulunan LGU employees enjoyed a good quality of facilities at work (mean=3.23). This implies that there were desirable amenities or useful services provided by the management of the organization to their employees in the accomplishment of their tasks. The finding is primarily attributed to the good fringe benefits (mean=3.40) and social security benefits provided by the LGU to them (mean=3.40).

Similarly, Kabacan LGU employees also enjoyed a good quality of facilities at work (mean=3.18). This implies that there were desirable amenities or useful services provided by the management of the organization to their employees in the accomplishment of their tasks. The finding is primarily ascribed to the good safety measures (mean=3.32) and welfare activities provided by the LGU (mean=3.32).

Lastly, Matalam LGU employees enjoyed a good quality of facilities at work (mean=3.04). This implies that there were desirable amenities or useful services provided by the management of the organization to their employees in the accomplishment of their tasks. The result is mainly attributed to the social security benefits (mean=3.21) and good fringe benefits (mean=3.05) provided by the LGU to them

Table 3.e

The Quality of Work Life in terms of Facilities of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD
During the COVID-19 pandemic,												
1. Fringe benefits provided are good.	3.05	A	3.11	A	3.14	A	3.35	SA	3.40	SA	3.21	A
2. My LGU provides the social security benefits.	3.21	A	3.46	SA	3.07	A	3.35	SA	3.40	SA	3.30	SA
3. Good transportation facilities are provided by the LGU.	2.95	A	3.37	SA	3.04	A	3.22	A	2.95	A	3.11	A
4. Safety measures adopted by the LGU are good.	3.00	A	3.51	SA	3.32	SA	3.57	SA	3.20	A	3.32	SA
5. Good welfare activities are provided by our LGU.	3.00	A	3.54	SA	3.32	SA	3.43	SA	3.20	A	3.30	SA
Overall	3.04	A	3.40	SA	3.18	Agree	3.38	SA	3.23	A	3.25	A

LEGEND:	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Agree (A)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Poor (P)

Quality of Work Life in terms of Job Satisfaction and Job Security of the Regular Employees

Table 3.f presents the quality of work-life in terms of job satisfaction and job security of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The study revealed that Tulunan LGU employees had an excellent quality of job satisfaction and job security (mean=3.45). This implies that they highly viewed their work as favorable to them. The finding is primarily attributed to their working conditions allow them to work as much as possible (mean=3.70) and condition of their work allowing them to be the best in a particular field (mean=3.61).

Carmen LGU employees had an excellent quality of job satisfaction and job security (mean=3.45). This implies that they very highly viewed their work as favorable to them. The finding is primarily attributed to the comfort and satisfaction (mean=3.54) and security they quite feel with their job (mean=3.43), good status of job security (mean=3.43), and condition of their work allowing them to be the best in a particular field(mean=3.43).

Matalam LGU employees also had a good quality of job satisfaction and job security (mean=3.45). This implies that they viewed their work as favorable to them. The finding is primarily attributed to the requirement of a strong trade union to protect employees' interests (mean=3.47), comfort and satisfaction (mean=3.37) and security they quite feel with their job (mean=3.37) as well as the good status of job security (mean=3.37).

M'lang LGU employees had a good quality of job satisfaction and job security (mean=3.18). This implies that they viewed their work as favorable to them. The finding is primarily attributed to the comfort and satisfaction (mean=3.26) and security they quite feel with their job (mean=3.26) as well as the condition of their work allowing them to be the best in a particular field(mean=3.26).

Kabacan LGU employees had agood quality of job satisfaction and job security (mean=3.16). This implies that they viewed their work as favorable to them. The finding is primarily attributed to the comfort and satisfaction (mean=3.39) and the condition of their work allowing them to be the best in a particular field (mean=3.29).

Table 3.f

The Quality of Work Life in terms of Job Satisfaction and Job Security of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD
During the COVID-19 pandemic,												
1. I feel comfortable and satisfied with my job.	3.37	SA	3.54	SA	3.39	SA	3.26	SA	3.50	SA	3.41	SA
2. I feel quite secured about my job.	3.37	SA	3.43	SA	3.11	A	3.26	SA	3.50	SA	3.33	SA
3. Conditions on my job allow me to be as productive as I could be.	3.32	SA	3.40	SA	3.21	A	3.17	A	3.70	SA	3.36	SA
4. A strong trade union is required to protect employees' interests.	3.47	SA	3.34	SA	3.11	A	3.22	A	3.30	SA	3.29	SA
5. The job security is good.	3.37	SA	3.43	SA	3.18	A	3.17	A	3.40	SA	3.31	SA
6. My earnings are fair when compared to the others doing the same type of work in other LGUs.	3.11	A	3.14	A	2.86	A	3.00	A	3.30	SA	3.08	A
7. The procedure followed for job rotation is good.	2.95	A	3.31	SA	3.14	A	3.13	A	3.30	SA	3.17	A
8. I feel that my work allows me to do my best in a particular area.	3.05	A	3.43	SA	3.29	SA	3.26	SA	3.60	SA	3.33	SA
Overall	3.25	A	3.38	SA	3.16	A	3.18	A	3.45	SA	3.28	SA

LEGEND:

Response Scale

Mean (M)

Qualitative Description (QD)

Interpretation

4

3.26-4.00

Strongly Agree (SA)

Excellent (E)

3

2.51-3.25

Agree (A)

Good (G)

2

1.76-2.50

Disagree (D)

Fair (F)

1

1.00-1.75

Strongly Disagree (SD)

Poor (P)

Quality of Work Life in terms of Autonomy of Work of the Regular Employees

Table 3.g presents the quality of work-life in terms of autonomy of work of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Based on their responses, Carmen LGU employees had a good quality of autonomy at work (mean=3.22). This implies that they enjoyed a desirable quality of independence at work in the performance of their task with less or without managerial or colleague assistance. Moreover, the finding is ascribed to their job qualities allowing them to use their skills and abilities (mean=3.54) and somework being allowed to be done from home (mean=3.31).

M'lang LGU employees had a good quality of autonomy of work (mean=3.22). This implies that they enjoyed a desirable quality of independence at work in the performance of their task with less or without managerial or colleague assistance. Moreover, the finding is ascribed to their job qualities, allowing them to use their skills and abilities (mean=3.52) and balance between objectives and resources provided in their organization (mean=3.43).

Kabacan LGU employees had a good quality of autonomy of work (mean=3.11). This implies that they enjoyed a desirable quality of independence at work in the performance of their task with less or without managerial or colleague assistance. Moreover, the finding is ascribed to their job qualities, allowing them to use their skills and abilities (mean=3.39) and balance between objectives and resources provided in their organization (mean=3.32).

Tulunan LGU employees had a good quality of autonomy of work (mean=3.08). This implies that they enjoyed a desirable quality of independence at work in the performance of their task with less or without managerial or colleague assistance. Further, the finding is assigned to their job qualities, allowing them to use their skills and abilities (mean=3.40), balance between objectives and resources provided in their organization (mean=3.20), and somework allowed to be done from home (mean=3.20).

Matalam LGU employees had a good quality of autonomy of work (mean=3.02). This implies that they enjoyed a desirable quality of independence at work in the performance of their task with less or without managerial or colleague assistance. Moreover, the finding is ascribed to their job qualities, allowing them to use their skills and abilities (mean=3.37) and balance between objectives and resources provided in their organization (mean=3.16).

Table 3.g

The Quality of Work Life in terms of Autonomy of Work of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD										
During the COVID-19 pandemic,												
1. My job lets me use my skills and abilities	3.37	SA	3.54	SA	3.39	SA	3.52	SA	3.40	SA	3.44	SA
2. My LGU allows a flexi-time option	3.00	A	3.20	A	3.21	A	3.09	A	2.90	A	3.08	A
3. A part of my job is allowed to be done at home.	2.95	A	3.31	SA	2.75	A	2.91	A	3.20	A	3.02	A
4. I find my work quite stressful	2.63	A	2.91	A	2.93	A	3.04	A	2.60	A	2.82	A
5. I am ready to take additional responsibilities with my job	3.00	A	3.11	A	3.04	A	3.35	SA	3.20	A	3.14	A
6. In our organization there is a balance between stated objectives and resources provided.	3.16	A	3.26	SA	3.32	SA	3.43	SA	3.20	A	3.27	SA
Overall	3.02	A	3.22	A	3.11	A	3.22	A	3.08	A	3.13	A

LEGEND:	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Agree (A)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Poor (P)

Quality of Work Life in terms of Adequacy of Resources of the Regular Employees

Table 3.h presents the quality of work-life in terms of adequacy of resources of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Based on their responses, Carmen LGU employees enjoyed an excellent number of resources at work (mean=3.33). This implies that materials, supplies, and communication and information channels for the employees necessary in facilitating performance and attainment of the organizational objectives were highly available. The result is attributed to the satisfactory communication and information flow between departments (mean=3.37) and presence of well-defined channels for exchanging and transferring information (mean=3.34).

Likewise, Tulunan LGU employees enjoyed an excellent number of resources at work (mean=3.27). This implies that materials, supplies, and communication and information channels for the employees necessary in facilitating performance and attainment of the organizational objectives were highly available. The finding is attributed to the provision of the LGU of resources to help them perform better (mean=3.40) and satisfactory communication and information flow between departments (mean=3.30).

M'lang LGU employees also enjoyed a good number of resources at work (mean=3.22). This implies that materials, supplies, and communication and information channels for the employees necessary in facilitating performance and attainment of the organizational objectives were available. The result is attributed to the satisfactory communication and information flow between departments (mean=3.26) and presence of well-defined channels for exchanging and transferring information (mean=3.22).

Kabacan LGU employees enjoyed a good number of resources at work (mean=3.07). This implies that materials, supplies, and communication and information channels for the employees necessary in facilitating performance and attainment of the organizational objectives were available. The result is primarily attributed to the provision of the LGU of resources to facilitate their performance (mean=3.14), satisfactory communication and information flow between departments (mean=3.04), and presence of well-defined channels for exchanging and transferring information (mean=3.04).

Matalam LGU employees enjoyed a good number of resources at work (mean=3.07). This implies that materials, supplies, and communication and information channels for the employees necessary in facilitating performance and attainment of the organizational objectives were available. The result is primarily attributed to the provision of the LGU of resources to help them perform better (mean=3.11) and satisfactory communication and information flow between departments (mean=3.11).

Table 3.h

The Quality of Work Life in terms of Adequacy of Resources of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD
During the COVID-19 pandemic,												
1. There are much defined channels for information exchange and transfer.	3.00	A	3.34	SA	3.04	A	3.22	A	3.10	A	3.14	A
2. My LGU provides resources to facilitate my performance.	3.11	A	3.29	SA	3.14	A	3.17	A	3.40	SA	3.22	A
3. Communication and information flow between the departments is satisfactory.	3.11	A	3.37	SA	3.04	A	3.26	SA	3.30	SA	3.19	A
Overall	3.07	A	3.33	SA	3.07	A	3.22	A	3.27	SA	3.19	A

LEGEND:	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Agree (A)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Poor (P)

Overall Quality of Work Life of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Table 3.i shows the overall quality of work-life of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The study revealed that they enjoyed a good quality of work-life during the COVID-19 pandemic (mean=3.21). This implies that they are happy and contented with the social and professional environment of their organization while performing tasks in the achievement of the objectives of the entire organization.

The finding contrasts the study of Weitzer, et al. (2021) conducted among working Austrian citizens which reported a significant decrease in the quality of life and perceived productivity of their respondents amid the pandemic suggesting that the mitigation of the crisis had affected the life of the Austrian working population negatively.

Furthermore, Ramos and Prasetyo (2020) concluded that observance of work from home arrangement during the pandemic has a significant effect on job satisfaction and productivity of various employees in different sectors in the Philippines. However, the research ascertained that most of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province observed a five-day work. Moreover, it failed to specifically describe the status of flexible work arrangement observed by the respondents during the pandemic. Hence, drawing an inference that the work arrangement they observed during the pandemic has something to do with the quality of work life they enjoy is not plausible.

LGU Carmen offers the best quality of work-life to regular employees during the COVID-19 pandemic. The finding unveiled that their regular employees enjoyed an excellent quality of work-life (mean=3.30). This is assigned to their exceptional facilities (Mean=3.40), job satisfaction and job security (mean=3.38), resources (mean=3.33), training and development (mean=3.31), and work environment (mean=3.30) as well as good relation and cooperation at work (mean=3.24), organization culture and climate (mean=3.23), and autonomy of work (mean=3.22).

LGU Tulan ranked next with Carmen. Similarly, the study ascertained that their regular employees enjoyed an excellent quality of work-life (mean=3.30). This is attributed to their exceptional relation and cooperation at work (Mean=3.53), job security and job satisfaction (mean=3.45), and training and development (mean=3.43) as well as good resources (mean=3.27), facilities (mean=3.23), work environment (mean=3.18), organization and culture (mean=3.14), and autonomy of work (mean=3.08).

LGU M'lang placed next after Tulan. Similarly, the study assessed that their regular employees enjoyed a good quality of work life (mean=3.24). This is attributed to their exceptional work environment (mean=3.43), facilities (mean=3.38), and relation and cooperation (mean=3.38) as well as good resources (mean=3.22), autonomy of work (mean=3.22), job satisfaction and job security (mean=3.18), organization culture and climate (mean=3.12), and training and development (mean=2.99).

LGU Kabacan has the ranked fourth among the five LGUs in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province. The research ascertained that their regular employees enjoyed a good quality of work life (mean=3.14). This is ascribed to their exceptional training and development (mean=3.28) as well as good relation and cooperation (mean=3.25), facilities (mean=3.18), job satisfaction and job security (mean=3.16), autonomy of work (mean=3.11), work environment (mean=3.10), resources (mean=3.07), and organization culture and climate (mean=2.93).

Lastly, the local government unit of Matalam had the lowest quality of work life among five LGUs in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the pandemic (mean=3.08). Nevertheless, it was described that their regular employees enjoyed a good quality of work life (mean=3.08). The finding is assigned to a desirable job satisfaction and job security (mean=3.25), work environment (mean=3.15), relation and cooperation (mean=3.12), resources (mean=3.07), organization culture and climate (mean=3.07), facilities (mean=3.04), autonomy of work (mean=3.02), and training and development (mean=2.94).

Table 3.i

The Quality of Work Life of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD
1. Work Environment	3.15	A	3.30	SA	3.10	A	3.43	SA	3.18	A	3.23	A
2. Organization Culture and Climate	3.07	A	3.23	A	2.93	A	3.12	A	3.14	A	3.10	A
3. Relation and Cooperation	3.12	A	3.24	A	3.25	A	3.38	SA	3.53	SA	3.30	SA
4. Training and Development	2.94	A	3.31	SA	3.28	SA	2.99	A	3.43	SA	3.19	A
5. Facilities	3.04	A	3.40	SA	3.18	A	3.38	SA	3.23	A	3.25	A
6. Job Satisfaction and Job Security	3.25	A	3.38	SA	3.16	A	3.18	A	3.45	SA	3.28	SA
7. Autonomy of Work	3.02	A	3.22	A	3.11	A	3.22	A	3.08	A	3.13	A
8. Adequacy of Resources	3.07	A	3.33	SA	3.07	A	3.22	A	3.27	A	3.19	A
Quality of Work Life of the Regular Employees in Every LGU	3.08	A	3.30	SA	3.14	A	3.24	A	3.29	SA	3.21	A
OVERALL	3.21	A										

LEGEND:	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Agree (A)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Poor (P)

Performance of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Examining employee performance is one of most significant concepts in organizational studies. It basically signifies one's achievement at work after exerting effort on a particular job. Goodhue (2011) indicated that the Human Resource Management (HRM) of every organization should focus on improving employee performance to ensure effective and high quality of work.

This section presents the performance of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior. Afterwards, overall finding on the performance of regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic is presented.

Performance in terms of Task Performance of the Regular Employees

Table 4.a presents the performance in terms of task performance of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Based on their responses, M'lang LGU employees had exhibited excellent task performance (mean=3.59). This implies that they highly manifest job explicit behaviors to respond to the given task assigned to them resulting to performance at work. The finding is primarily ascribed to their ability to separate main issues from side issues at work (mean=3.65) as well as the job done with a minimum of time and effort (mean=3.65).

It was divulged that Tulunan LGU employees had exhibited excellent task performance (mean=3.56). This implies that they highly manifest job explicit behaviors to respond to the given task assigned to them resulting to performance at work. The finding is primarily ascribed to their ability to keep the outcomes they need at work (mean=3.80) as well as the job done with a minimum of time and effort (mean=3.80).

The research ascertain that Kabacan LGU employees had exhibited excellent task performance (mean=3.51). This implies that they highly manifest job explicit behaviors to respond to the given task assigned to them resulting to performance at work. The finding is mainly assigned to their ability to schedule their task in such a way that it will be completed on time (mean=3.71) as well as keep in mind the results that they have to achieve at work (mean=3.54).

It was described that Carmen LGU employees had exhibited excellent task performance (mean=3.47). This implies that they highly manifest job explicit behaviors to respond to the given task assigned to them resulting to performance at work. The finding is primarily attributed to their ability to keep the outcomes they need at work (mean=3.54), separate main issues from side issues at work (mean=3.51) and perform their work well with minimal time and effort (mean=3.51).

It was found that Matalam LGU employees had exhibited excellent task performance (mean=3.36). This implies that they highly manifest job explicit behaviors to respond to the given task assigned to them resulting to performance at work. The finding is primarily attributed to their ability to schedule their task in such a way that it will be completed on time (mean=3.47) as well as the job done with a minimum of time and effort (mean=3.42).

Table 4.a

The Performance in terms of Task Performance of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD										
In the past three (3) months,												
1. I managed to plan my work so that it was done on time.	3.47	A	3.49	A	3.71	A	3.52	A	3.80	A	3.60	A
2. My planning was optimal.	3.26	A	3.29	A	3.36	A	3.39	A	3.20	O	3.30	A
3. I kept in mind the results that I have to achieve in my work.	3.32	A	3.54	A	3.54	A	3.74	A	3.80	A	3.59	A
4. I was able to separate main issues from side issues at work.	3.32	A	3.51	A	3.46	A	3.65	A	3.60	A	3.51	A
5. I was able to perform my work well with minimal time and effort.	3.42	A	3.51	A	3.46	A	3.65	A	3.40	A	3.49	A
Overall	3.36	A	3.47	A	3.51	A	3.59	A	3.56	A	3.50	A

LEGEND	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Agree (A)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Poor (P)

Performance in terms of Contextual Performance of the Regular Employees

Table 4.b presents the performance in terms of contextual performance of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The study assessed that Tulanang LGU employees had exhibited excellent contextual performance (mean=3.60). This implies that they highly volunteer for extra job, work with enthusiasm and help and cooperate with others at work. The finding is attributed to their effort at keeping their job knowledge (mean=3.90) and skills up-to-date (mean=3.80).

Likewise, M'lang LGU employees had exhibited excellent contextual performance (mean=3.50). This implies that they highly volunteer for extra job, work with enthusiasm and help and cooperate with others at work. The finding is attributed to their effort at keeping their job knowledge up-to-date (mean=3.61) and coming up with creative solutions to new problems (mean=3.61).

Kabacan LGU employees had exhibited excellent contextual performance (mean=3.41). This implies that they highly volunteer for extra job, work with enthusiasm and help and cooperate with others at work. The finding is attributed to their effort at keeping their job skills (mean=3.57) and knowledge up-to-date (mean=3.54).

Carmen LGU employees had exhibited excellent contextual performance (mean=3.41). This implies that they highly volunteer for extra job, work with enthusiasm and help and cooperate with others at work. The finding is attributed to their effort at actively participating in work meetings (mean=3.49) and taking on extra responsibilities (mean=3.49).

Matalam LGU employees also had exhibited excellent contextual performance (mean=3.35). This implies that they highly volunteer for extra job, work with enthusiasm and help and cooperate with others at work. The finding is attributed to their effort at coming up with creative solutions to new problems (mean=3.47) and keeping their job knowledge (mean=3.42) and skills up-to-date (mean=3.42).

Table 4.b

The Performance in terms of Contextual Performance of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD										
In the past three (3) months,												
1. I took on extra responsibilities.	3.37	A	3.49	A	3.46	A	3.43	A	3.50	A	3.45	A
2. I started new tasks myself when my old ones were finished.	3.37	A	3.46	A	3.32	A	3.52	A	3.40	A	3.41	A
3. I took on challenging work tasks, when available.	3.21	O	3.31	A	3.43	A	3.48	A	3.50	A	3.39	A
4. I worked at keeping my job knowledge up-to-date.	3.42	A	3.37	A	3.54	A	3.61	A	3.90	A	3.57	A
5. I worked at keeping my job skills up-to-date	3.42	A	3.43	A	3.57	A	3.57	A	3.80	A	3.56	A
6. I came up with creative solutions to new problems.	3.47	A	3.34	A	3.32	A	3.61	A	3.60	A	3.47	A
7. I kept looking for new challenges in my job.	3.21	O	3.40	A	3.32	A	3.39	A	3.50	A	3.36	A
8. I actively participated in work meetings.	3.32	A	3.49	A	3.29	A	3.39	A	3.60	A	3.42	A
Overall	3.35	A	3.41	A	3.41	A	3.50	A	3.60	A	3.45	A

LEGEND	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Agree (A)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Poor (P)

Performance in terms of Counterproductive Work Behavior of the Regular Employees

Table 4.c presents the performance in terms of contextual performance of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The study assessed that Carmen LGU employees had exhibited a lower degree of counterproductive work behavior (mean=2.07). This implies that employees hardly exhibit disobedience of work rules and norms observed by all in the organization. The finding is mostly attributed to their behavior of speaking with their colleagues about the negative aspects of their work (mean=2.31) and making problems greater than they were at work (mean=2.20).

Likewise, Tulunan LGU employees had exhibited a lower degree of counterproductive work behavior (mean=1.84). This implies that employees hardly exhibit disobedience of work rules and norms observed by all in the organization. The finding is mostly attributed to their behavior of complaining about unimportant matters at work (mean=2.30) and speaking with their colleagues about the negative aspects of their work (mean=2.20).

Kabacan LGU employees had exhibited a lower degree of counterproductive work behavior (mean=1.79). This implies that employees hardly exhibit disobedience of work rules and norms observed by all in the organization. The finding is mostly attributed to their behavior of speaking with their colleagues about the negative aspects of their work (mean=2.04) and complaining about unimportant matters at work (mean=1.96).

Matalam LGU employees revealed that counterproductive work behavior was not at all observed by the regular employees (mean=1.75). This implies that employees did not exhibit disobedience of work rules and norms observed by all in the organization. Nevertheless, the study unveiled that they scarcely manifested behavior of complaining about unimportant matters at work (mean=2.00) and speaking with their colleagues about the negative aspects of their work (mean=1.89).

M'lang LGU employees uncovered that counterproductive work behavior was not at all observed by the regular employees (mean=1.66). This implies that employees did not exhibit disobedience of work rules and norms observed by all in the organization. Nonetheless, the study divulged that they scarcely manifested behavior of complaining about unimportant matters at work (mean=1.91) and making problems greater than they were at work (mean=1.78).

Table 4.c

The Performance in terms of Counterproductive Work Behavior of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD										
In the past three (3) months,												
1. I complained about unimportant matters at work.	2.00	R	2.17	R	1.96	R	1.91	R	2.30	R	2.07	R
2. I made problems greater than they were at work.	1.47	N	2.20	R	1.61	N	1.78	R	1.60	N	1.73	N
3. I focused on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects.	1.63	N	1.69	N	1.50	N	1.48	N	1.60	N	1.58	N
4. I spoke with colleagues about the negative aspects of my work.	1.89	R	2.31	R	2.04	R	1.61	N	2.20	R	2.01	R
5. I spoke with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of my work.	1.74	N	2.00	Rarely	1.82	R	1.52	N	1.50	N	1.72	N
Overall	1.75	N	2.07	R	1.79	R	1.66	N	1.84	R	1.82	R

LEGEND:	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Agree (A)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Poor (P)

Overall Performance of the Regular LGU Employees in the Third District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Table 4.d shows the overall performance of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

It was ascertained in the study that the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province exhibited a moderate level of performance during the COVID-19 pandemic. This implies that they frequently exhibit both effective efforts and outcomes and negative behaviors at work during the pandemic either attaining or undermining the organizational objectives.

Tulunan LGU employees performed the best during the COVID-19 crisis. The study ascertained that their regular employees had exhibited a moderate level performance during the pandemic (mean=3.00). This is attributed to a high level of contextual performance (mean=3.60) and task performance (mean=3.56) as well as low level of counter productive work behavior (mean=1.84) they showed at work during the pandemic.

Carmen LGU employees ranked next with Tulunan. Similarly, the study ascertained that their regular employees had exhibited a moderate level performance during the pandemic (mean=2.98). This is ascribed to a high level of task performance (mean=3.46) and contextual performance (mean=3.41) as well as low level of counter productive work behavior (mean=2.07) they showed at work during the pandemic.

M'lang LGU employees ranked next with Carmen. The study ascertained that their regular employees had exhibited a moderate level performance during the pandemic (mean=2.92). This is ascribed to a high level of task performance (mean=3.59) and contextual performance (mean=3.50) as well as low level of counter productive work behavior (mean=1.06) they showed at work during the pandemic.

Kabacan LGU employees ranked next with M'lang. Similarly, the study ascertained that their regular employees had exhibited a moderate level performance during the pandemic (mean=2.90). This is ascribed to a high level of task performance (mean=3.51) and contextual performance (mean=3.41) as well as low level of counterproductive work behavior (mean=1.79) they showed at work during the pandemic.

Among the five (5) LGUs in the 3rd District of the Cotabato Province, the regular employees of the local government of Matalam had exhibited the lowest performance during the COVID-19 crisis. Moreover, it was assessed that their regular employees had exhibited a moderate level performance during the pandemic (mean=2.92). This is ascribed to a high level of task performance (mean=3.36) and contextual performance (mean=3.35) as well as low level of counterproductive work behavior (mean=1.75) they showed at work during the pandemic.

Meanwhile, the COVID-19 outbreak had left almost all the employees around the globe to work in a totally different setting compared to the traditional face-to-face operations. Narayanamurthy and Tortorella (2021) mentioned that the work implications of the COVID-19 such as home office work

environment, job insecurity and virtual connection have an impact on employee’s performance during the crisis. They mentioned that many organizations faced a significant reduction in their demands because of lock downs and social distancing restrictions implemented by governments around the world leading to job instability. Moreover, they explicated that many organizations restructured their work settings into home office environment. This was agreed by Deole, Deter, and Huang (2021) who added that working from home is associated with a higher self-perceived productivity. They concluded that a positive linkage between work from home and performance is stronger for those who travel longer distance to work and had a higher work autonomy.

Furthermore, Narayanamurthy and Tortorella (2021) cited that communication barriers were some of the biggest problems entailed by the pandemic among organizations since physical interaction was constrained by governments to contain the spread of the virus. To curb such restriction, online communication tools were more extensively utilized, but many had encountered difficulty in employing virtual communication primarily due to poor internet connection in their own localities.

Table 4.d
The Performance of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Variable and Its Dimensions	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD
1. Task Performance	3.36	A	3.47	A	3.51	A	3.59	A	3.56	A	3.50	A
2. Contextual Performance	3.35	A	3.41	A	3.41	A	3.50	A	3.60	A	3.45	A
3. Counterproductive Work Behavior	1.75	R	2.07	R	1.79	R	1.66	N	1.84	R	1.82	R
Performance of the Regular Employees in Every LGU	2.82	O	2.98	O	2.90	O	2.92	O	3.00	O	2.92	O
OVERALL	2.92	O										

LEGEND:	Response Scale	Mean (M)	Qualitative Description (QD)	Interpretation
	4	3.26-4.00	Always (A)	Excellent (E)
	3	2.51-3.25	Often (O)	Good (G)
	2	1.76-2.50	Rarely (R)	Fair (F)
	1	1.00-1.75	None (N)	Poor (P)

Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) Rating of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic

During the strategic planning where activities done, success indicators of activities are established before the start of performance period. The Philippine Coconut Authority (2020), Department of Agriculture under the Office of the President, indicated that these shall serve as bases for various offices and every employee in the Philippine government in preparing rating forms and performance contract. Like the previous performance evaluation systems implemented, the strategic performance management system (SPMS) adopts the semi-annual periods from January to June and July to December. The new system uses two forms – the Department Heads and Division Chiefs complete the Office Performance Commitment and Review (OPCR) Form, while individual workers complete the Individual Performance Commitment and Review (IPCR) Form – accomplished by individual personnel. All offices in every local government unit in the country set their respective goals by completing the OPCR’s first four columns and the IPCR’s first two columns. This is done before both rating periods begin.

Table 5 presents the Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) rating of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic. The finding revealed that the regular employees have a very satisfactory IPCR rating as they accomplished 90-99.99% of their targets (mean=4.13). Furthermore, the study divulged that the regular employees in the municipality of Kabacan has the highest IPCR rating with a very satisfactory rating as they accomplished 90-99.99% of their targets (mean=4.23). It was followed by the municipality of Matalam with a very satisfactory rating as they accomplished 90-99.99% of their targets (mean=4.18). Third is the municipality of Tulunan with a very satisfactory rating as they accomplished 90-99.99% of their targets (mean=4.15). The municipality of M’lang followed with a very satisfactory rating as they accomplished 90-99.99% of their targets (mean=4.07). Lastly, the regular employees of the municipality of Carmen have the lowest IPCR rating with a very satisfactory rating as they accomplished 90-99.99% of their targets (mean=4.04).

Table 5

The Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) Rating of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

Statements	MATALAM		CARMEN		KABACAN		MLANG		TULUNAN		Overall	
	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD	M	QD
During the COVID-19 pandemic,												
1. IPCR Targets Accomplished during January to June 2020.	4.16	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.06	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.21	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.04	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.15	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.12	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished
2. IPCR Targets Accomplished during July to December 2020.	4.21	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.03	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.25	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.09	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.15	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.15	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished
IPCR Rating in Every LGU	4.18	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.04	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.23	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.07	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.15	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	4.13	90-79.99% of the Targets are Accomplished
OVERALL	4.13	70-79.99% of the target are accomplished										

Response Scale	Mean Scale	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	100% of the Targets are Accomplished	Outstanding (O)
4	3.50-4.49	90-99.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	Very Satisfactory (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	80-89.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	Satisfactory (S)
2	1.50-2.49	70-79.99% of the Targets are Accomplished	Unsatisfactory (U)
1	1.00-1.49	Below 70% of the Targets are Accomplished	Poor (P)

Relationship between Quality of Work Life and Performance of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Table 6 presents the test of relationship between quality of work-life and performance. The overall correlation coefficient value of .76 with a p-value lower than .05 signified rejection of the null hypothesis showing that there is a significant relationship between quality of work-life and performance. This implies that the quality of work-life is positively correlated with performance; meaning, as the quality of work-life of the regular employees improves, their performance becomes better.

Moreover, the study also determined that some of the dimensions of quality of work-life have a significant relationship with the dimensions of performance. Firstly, the study determined that work environment is significantly associated with the respondents' task performance ($r_s=.34$; $p=.04$) and counterproductive work behavior ($r_s=.23$; $p=.17$). Moreover, it was determined that their work environment is positively correlated with their task performance and counterproductive work behavior; meaning, as their work environment improves, their degree of task performance and counterproductive work behavior also increases. On the other hand, no significant relationship was found between work environment and contextual performance ($r_s=.06$; $p=.72$).

Secondly, it was determined that organization culture and climate has a significant relationship with their task performance ($r_s=.38$; $p=.02$), contextual performance ($r_s=.48$; $p=.00$), and counterproductive work behavior ($r_s=.41$; $p=.01$). Furthermore, it was determined that their organization culture and climate is positively correlated with their task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior; meaning, as their organization culture and climate improves, their degree of task performance, contextual performance and counterproductive work behavior also increases.

Similarly, the research determined that relation and cooperation has a significant relationship with their task performance ($r_s=.56$; $p<.001$), contextual performance ($r_s=.62$; $p<.001$), and counterproductive work behavior ($r_s=.47$; $p=.00$). Furthermore, it was determined that their relation and cooperation is positively correlated with their task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior; meaning, as their relation and cooperation at work improves, their degree of task performance, contextual performance and counterproductive work behavior also increases.

Fourthly, study also determined that training and development has a significant relationship with their task performance ($r_s=.72$; $p<.001$), contextual performance ($r_s=.42$; $p=.01$), and counterproductive work behavior ($r_s=.50$; $p=.00$). Furthermore, it was determined that their training and development is positively correlated with their task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior; meaning, as their training and development at work improves, their degree of task performance, contextual performance and counterproductive work behavior also increases.

Fifthly, it was determined that facilities is significantly associated with the respondents' counterproductive work behavior ($r_s=.39$; $p=.01$). Moreover, it was found that their facilities is positively correlated with their counterproductive work behavior; meaning, as their facilities improve, their degree of

counterproductive work behavior also increases. On the other hand, no significant relationship was found between facilities and task performance ($r_s=.28$; $p=.10$). and contextual performance ($r_s=.27$; $p=.11$).

Furthermore, study also determined that job satisfaction and job security has a significant relationship with their task performance ($r_s=.54$; $p<.001$), contextual performance ($r_s=.37$; $p=.02$), and counterproductive work behavior ($r_s=.51$; $p<.001$). Furthermore, it was determined that their job satisfaction and job security is positively correlated with their task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior; meaning, as their job satisfaction and job security improves, their degree of task performance, contextual performance and counterproductive work behavior also increases.

Further, it was determined that autonomy of work has a significant relationship with their task performance ($r_s=.47$; $p=.00$), contextual performance ($r_s=.22$; $p=.20$), and counterproductive work behavior ($r_s=.38$; $p=.02$). Furthermore, it was determined that their autonomy of work is positively correlated with their task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior; meaning, as their autonomy of work improves, their degree of task performance, contextual performance and counterproductive work behavior also increases.

Lastly, it was determined that adequacy of resources has a significant relationship with their task performance ($r_s=.33$; $p=.04$), contextual performance ($r_s=.46$; $p=.00$), and counterproductive work behavior ($r_s=.53$; $p<.001$). Furthermore, it was determined that their adequacy of resources is positively correlated with their task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior; meaning, as the number of their resources increases, their degree of task performance, contextual performance and counterproductive work behavior also increases.

Furthermore, the result of there search is congruent with the findings of Hamad (2018) and Cross and Daniel (2020) who indicated the significant association between quality of work-life and employee performance. Firstly, Hamad (2018) concluded that quality ofwork-life is positively and meaningfully correlated with employee performance. This means that as the quality of work-life improves, the performance of the employees will also improve. Similar was indicated by Cross and Daniel (2020) who also affirmed the significant relationship of the two. It was further mentioned that as the quality of work-life and performance of the employees improve, the performance of the whole organization will also get better.

Table 6
Relationship between Quality of Work Life and Performance of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

QUALITY OF WORK LIFE	PERFORMANCE		
	$r=.76^*$ $p<.001$		
	<i>Task Performance</i>	<i>Contextual Performance</i>	<i>Counterproductive Work Behavior</i>
<i>Work Environment</i>	$r_s=.34^*$ $p=.04$	$r_s=.06$ $p=.72$	$r_s=.23$ $p=.17$
<i>Organization Culture and Climate</i>	$r_s=.38^*$ $p=.02$	$r_s=.48^{**}$ $p=.00$	$r_s=.41^*$ $p=.01$
<i>Relation and Cooperation</i>	$r_s=.56^{**}$ $p<.001$	$r_s=.62^{**}$ $p<.001$	$r_s=.47^{**}$ $p=.00$
<i>Training and Development</i>	$r_s=.72^{**}$ $p<.001$	$r_s=.42^*$ $p=.01$	$r_s=.50^{**}$ $p=.00$
<i>Facilities</i>	$r_s=.28$ $p=.10$	$r_s=.27$ $p=.11$	$r_s=.39^*$ $p=.01$
<i>Job Satisfaction and Job Security</i>	$r_s=.54^{**}$ $p<.001$	$r_s=.37^*$ $p=.02$	$r_s=.51^{**}$ $p<.001$
<i>Autonomy of Work</i>	$r_s=.47^{**}$ $p=.00$	$r_s=.22$ $p=.20$	$r_s=.38^*$ $p=.02$
<i>Adequacy of Resources</i>	$r_s=.33^*$	$r_s=.46^{**}$	$r_s=.53^{**}$

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Relationship between Quality of Work Life and Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) Rating of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Table 7 presents the test of relationship between quality of work-life and the Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR). The overall correlation coefficient value of .53 with a p-value lower than .05 signified rejection of the null hypothesis showing that there is a significant relationship between quality of work-life and the IPCR rating. This implies that the quality of work-life is positively correlated with the IPCR rating, meaning, as the quality of work-life of the regular employees improves, their IPCR rating becomes better.

Furthermore, the study determined that some of the dimensions of quality of work-life are significantly associated with the IPCR rating. Specifically, work environment ($r_s=.42$; $p=.01$), relation and cooperation ($r_s=.40$; $p=.01$), training and development ($r_s=.46$; $p=.00$), job satisfaction and job security ($r_s=.44$; $p=.00$), and autonomy of work ($r_s=.50$; $p=.00$) were found to be significantly associated with the respondents' IPCR rating. Moreover, a positive correlation is found between work environment, relation and cooperation, training and development, job satisfaction and job security, autonomy of work and the respondents' IPCR rating; meaning, as these dimensions of quality of work-life improve, their IPCR rating will be enhanced. On the other hand, no significant relationship is found between organization culture and climate ($r_s=.21$; $p=.22$), facilities ($r_s=.19$; $p=.25$), adequacy of resources ($r_s=.27$; $p=.10$).

Table 7

Relationship between Quality of Work Life and Individual Performance Commitment Review of the Regular LGU Employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 Pandemic, March 2021

INDIVIDUAL PERFORMANCE COMMITMENT REVIEW	QUALITY OF WORK LIFE							
	$r=.53^{**}$ $p=<.001$							
	Work Environment	Organization Culture and Climate	Relation and Cooperation	Training and Development	Facilities	Job Satisfaction and Job Security	Autonomy of Work	Adequacy of Resources
	$r_s=.42^*$ $p=.01$	$r_s=.21$ $p=.22$	$r_s=.40^*$ $p=.01$	$r_s=.46^{**}$ $p=.00$	$r_s=.19$ $p=.25$	$r_s=.44^{**}$ $p=.00$	$r_s=.50^{**}$ $p=.00$	$r_s=.27$ $p=.10$
* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).								
** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).								

SUMMARY

The study is a descriptive-correlation research. It generally aimed to determine the significant relationship between quality of work-life and performance of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of the Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study involved 125 regular employees selected through stratified random sampling from five municipal local government units, namely Matalam, Carmen, Kabacan, Mlang, and Tulunan.

The following are the findings of the study:

1. A good quality of work-life was enjoyed by the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, an excellent quality of work-life is enjoyed by the regular LGU employees in the municipalities of Carmen and Tulunan, while a good quality of work-life is enjoyed by the regular LGU employees in Mlang, Kabacan, and Matalam.
2. A moderate level of performance was revealed among the regular employees in the five municipal local governments in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 crisis.
3. A very satisfactory Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) rating was demonstrated by the regular employees in the five (5) municipal local governments in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province during the COVID-19 outbreak.
4. There is a significant relationship between the quality of work-life and performance of the regular LGU employees during the pandemic.
5. There is a significant relationship between the quality of work-life and Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) rating of the regular LGU employees during the pandemic.

CONCLUSIONS

In light of the findings, the following conclusions were formulated:

The regular employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province enjoyed and were contented with the social and environmental aspects of their agencies' while performing tasks assigned to them to achieve the objectives of the entire agency. It can be inferred that during the COVID-19 pandemic, the regular LGU employees under study experience good to excellent quality of work-life.

The Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) rating of the regular employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province was very satisfactory, which it can be inferred that as the quality of work-life improved, the IPCR rating of the regular LGU employees could get better despite the COVID-19 crisis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The suggested points below intend to improve the quality of work-life and performance of the respondents as well as address the limitations of the study.

The Local Government Units in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province may continue on improving and increasing the quality of work-life of their regular employees in terms of their work environment, organization culture and climate, training and development, work autonomy, work facilities, and adequacy of resources, as these were found to be the lowest components of excellent work-life quality.

The LGU employees may improve their performance by working on the domains of quality of work-life that are significantly correlated with their performance.

The IPCR rating of the regular LGU employees may be improved the dimensions of quality of work-life that have a meaningfully positive relationship with their IPCR rating, such as the work environment, relation and cooperation, training and development, job satisfaction and job security, and autonomy of work.

As the scope of the study is limited to determining the significant relationship between quality of work-life and performance of the regular LGU employees in the 3rd District of Cotabato Province, future researchers may broaden the scope to include a region or different legislative districts in the province.

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